

Development of the PRATIC-b Soluble-Boron–Controlled Core and Benchmarking Using APOLLO2-CRONOS2, CMS5 and APOLLO3

Aimeric Eustache^{1*}, Geraud Prulhière¹, Romain Vuiart²

¹ French Atomic Energy and Alternative Energy Commission (CEA) DES/IRESNE/DER/SPRC/LE2C
Cadarache, Bldg. 230 F-13108 Saint-Paul-Lez-Durance, France

²Autorité de Sûreté Nucléaire et de Radioprotection (ASNR), PSN-RES/SNC/LN,
F-92260, Fontenay-aux-Roses, France

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803426

ABSTRACT

Neutronics code to code comparisons have been performed on the soluble-boron-free (SBF) small modular reactor (SMR) PRATIC, with APOLLO2-CRONOS2 and CMS5 code systems in previous work. These comparisons have been extended in this paper, on a new version of the PRATIC benchmark using soluble boron to accommodate the core reactivity and employing the additional code system APOLLO3. This new core, designated PRATIC-b, is a simpler SMR object technology than a SBF SMR. It can be used to perform code-to-code comparisons on basic applications while utilizing an industrial-grade SMR design. PRATIC-b is defined in this paper and its equilibrium cycle is computed with the three deterministic code systems: APOLLO2-CRONOS2, CMS5 and APOLLO3. PRATIC-b equilibrium cycle was characterised and the three codes show a good agreement on the analysed observable: equilibrium cycle length, reactivity control, critical boron concentration and core power distribution. Specifically, the difference in power peak estimations between the codes was smaller when using soluble boron reactivity control with PRATIC-b than with control rods in SBF-PRATIC.

Keywords: Neutronics, SMR, PWR, Equilibrium Core

1. INTRODUCTION

With the development of small modular reactors (SMRs), nuclear energy has the potential to fulfil a new role in addressing the decarbonization of the energy sector. SMRs could provide low-carbon, dispatchable energy production solutions for new intensive uses, such as industrial electrification and new digital infrastructure. Indeed, their smaller size could enable an installation closer to new end big electrical consumers [1] and allow a higher degree of standardisation that could reduce the costs and the lead time construction [2].

In order to study SMR concepts, an academic core neutronics benchmark, named PRATIC, was created in 2024 at the French Atomic Energy and Alternative Energy Commission (CEA) [3]. PRATIC belongs to the soluble-boron-free (SBF) pressurised water reactor (PWR) reactor type and utilises control rods to accommodate for reactivity losses during normal operation. The PRATIC benchmark was examined using a variety of code systems in 2024-2025 [4] and has integrated since international benchmarks, such as the EASI-SMR European project [5] and the Working Party on Scientific Issues and Uncertainty Analysis of Reactor System (WPRS) project at NEA [6]. Modelling of SBF-SMR can be difficult because these cores require large quantities of burnable absorbers and control rods to manage reactivity, as well as steel reflectors. Together, these components introduce significant spatial heterogeneities and cause strong variations in power distribution during the cycle, creating historical effects that challenge two-step deterministic schemes [3][4]. In order to extend the code-to-code comparison on a PRATIC SMR-like core, a new PRATIC core neutronic design was developed at CEA aiming to establish an application

*e-mail: aimericeustache@cea.fr

case simpler for modelling. This new core benchmark, designated PRATIC-b, incorporates soluble boron to control the reactivity and reduce the number of burnable poisons. As it is a small core, with a high amount of neutron leakage, it was decided to keep the steel radial reflector component of the SBF-PRATIC design.

The equilibrium cycle of PRATIC-b will be compared in this paper using three code systems: APOLLO2-CRONOS [7][8], APOLLO3 [9] and CMS5 [10][11]. The objective is to confirm the consistency of these codes, which have already been used to model the SBF PRATIC core, on a simpler SMR neutronics design. To draw these comparisons, this paper first details the codes used, then presents the new PRATIC-b equilibrium core and finally discusses the differences for the following observables: equilibrium cycle length, burnup distribution, reactivity control and power distribution.

The new PRATIC-b benchmark, developed by CEA, complements and extends the existing PRATIC database, available on a dedicated GIT repository licensed under CC BY-NC-SA 4.0, permitting data reuse for non-commercial purposes with proper attribution to the authors. Access to the repository can be requested by e-mail at pratic@cea.fr.

2. NEUTRONICS CODES AND CALCULATION SCHEMES

The present paper proposes to compute the equilibrium cycle of the PRATIC-b core with three deterministic neutronics code systems, using the same recommended options as those used in [4]:

- APOLLO2-CRONOS2: The French code system APOLLO2-CRONOS2, developed by CEA, was originally utilised to establish the inaugural PRATIC core [3]. APOLLO2.8-5 [7] generate 2-group homogenised macroscopic cross sections at assembly scale for the core calculation. A SHEM-MOC method [12] is employed to solve the 2D stationary transport equation, using a 281-group data based on the JEFF-3.1.1 evaluation [13] and a P3 anisotropic approximation. The diffusion equation is solved in CRONOS2 with the MINOS solver [14] on a pin-by-pin spatial mesh, integrating 20 meshes for the axial description of the fissile zone, each 10 cm high, and 4 meshes of 5 cm in each axial reflector.
- APOLLO3: APOLLO3 is the new deterministic code for lattice and core calculations, developed by CEA with the financial support of EDF and Framatome, which can modelized a wide range of reactor types from PWR to fast neutron reactors [9]. In this study, similar methods as APOLLO2-CRONOS2 are employed in APOLLO3 (JEFF 3.1.1, P3 anisotropic, SHEM-MOC, MINOS ...). Furthermore, the SIGAR python API [15] was used to facilitate the construction of the data set and ensure good coherence between the lattice and the core steps.
- CMS5: CMS5 (Core Management System version 5) stands for the assembling of the lattice code CASMO5 [10] and the core code SIMULATE5 [11]. In this paper, CASMO5 apply the collision probability method (P_{ij}) with a 586 energy groups library on coarse spatial meshes and in a second time employs a Method of Characteristics (MoC) with 19 energy-groups [16]. A nuclear data library based on the JEFF3.1.1 was also used for CMS5 in this paper but employing a P0 corrected isotropic approximation, which is the standard recommendation for this code. Contrary to CRONOS2 and APOLLO3, a simplified radial mesh was selected in SIMULATE5, consisting of a six by six uneven meshes (a submesh of even quarter assembly meshes) [17]. SIMULATE5 is able to perform pin power reconstruction in all the core, thus enabling the computation of three-dimensional pin power peak.

For more conveniency, as no assembly calculations are shown in this paper, the APOLLO2-CRONOS2, APOLLO3 and CMS5 results will be designated by only the core code names (CRONOS2, APOLLO3 and CMS5). In all the core simulations, thermohydraulic feedbacks are activated using a simplified radial mesh (quarter assembly meshes), and whole core calculation are computed. For the core depletion calculations, the ^{135}I - ^{135}Xe depletion sub-chain is artificially saturated at all time steps, in order to facilitate the code-to-code comparisons. Thus, for each step, a micro-evolution of the ^{135}I and the ^{135}Xe isotopes is performed in order to deduce its concentration once balanced.

This paper presents the equilibrium cycle of the PRATIC-b core. The equilibrium refers to the result of the equilibrium cycle search which aims, through a successive reloading of the fuels and cycle depletion calculation, to converge the burnup distribution and the cycle length. The end of cycle (EOC) criteria is reached when the critical boron concentration falls below 10 ppm, a value coherent with standard PWR

experience in France [18] and with the SBF PRATIC core EOC criteria which was established to 100 pcm [3]. The end of the equilibrium cycle search process is reached when the difference between one cycle length and the previous one is less or equal to 15 MWd/t.

3. DEFINITION OF THE NEW PRATIC-B CORE

The new PRATIC-b core was defined under the assumption that the loading pattern would remain identical to that of the SBF-PRATIC and hence only the fuel assembly enrichment, amount of gadolinium and absorber rods definition would be adapted. An optimization exercise was performed with these hypotheses following the same approach used for the PRATIC definition in 2024 [3]. The optimization was accomplished with the same criteria, including a cycle length close to the two years, a maximum linear power under 300 W/cm and an axial integrated maximum pin power under the saturation power factor. All other PRATIC-b core specifications are taken from the SBF PRATIC [3] and summarized in table 1. Specially, the same thermal-hydraulic specifications have been selected, such as the inlet temperature and the moderator flow rate. Geometrical data are detailed in the SBF PRATIC benchmark [3] and are not recalled here. The average linear power is the same as the SBF PRATIC [3], meaning that the three-dimensional power peak factors can be directly compared.

Table 1 : PRATIC core operating conditions at full power.

Data	Value
Nominal power (NP)	350 MW _{th}
Average linear power at 100 % NP ($^{AVE}P_{lin}$)	115.97 W/cm
Specific power density	24.73 W/g
Number of fuel assemblies	57
Primary circuit pressure	155 bars
Moderator inlet temperature at 100 % NP	285°C
Moderator flow rate	1550 kg.m ⁻² .s ⁻¹

3.1. Fuel assembly definition

PRATIC-b uses three different assemblies, classified by their position in the core as: central, internal and external as specified in table 2. Contrary to the original SBF PRATIC core [3], the internal assembly is the same as the central one and the only difference resides in the number of irradiation cycles performed. All the assemblies include only 8 gadolinium poisoned fuel rods and the same 8 wt.% gadolinium content with a 2.5 wt.% ²³⁵U enriched UO₂ support as [3], coherent with large PWR concept [18].

Table II. Definition of the fuel assemblies loaded in the PRATIC-b core.

Assembly	Enrichment in ²³⁵ U	Number of gadolinium poisoned fuel rods	Number of irradiation cycle
Central	2.5 %	8	1
Internal	2.5 %	8	2
External	5 %	8	2

The positions of the fuel, gadolinium poisoned fuel rods, guide tubes and the instrumentation tubes are identical for every assembly and are given in figure 1. AIC (80%Ag-15%In-5%Cd absorbent alloy) is employed for all the absorber rod cluster bank (black bank) and no steel (grey bank) is used contrary to SBF PRATIC [3]. For lattice depletion calculation, an averaged boron concentration of 850 ppm to 1000 ppm depending on the code used is employed all along the cycle, with a nominal temperature for the fuel (470°C) and nominal temperature and pressure for the moderator (300°C at 155 bar).

Figure 1 : Schematic view of absorber rods and gadolinium poisoned fuel rods distribution in the assembly.

3.2. Core configuration, management and reactivity control

The fuel management is the same as in the SBF PRATIC core [3] including a two-batch reloading scheme (except for the one cycle central assembly) and a rotational quarter symmetry for the fuel as illustrated in figure 3. Soluble boric acid with a natural isotopic abundance is used to control the long-term reactivity sweep. Absorbing rods have been added to shut down the core and control the reactivity in low power regime, reducing boron concentration and enhancing response time to fast power regime changes. At full power, all the control rods are extracted from the core, meaning that the reactivity is only managed by the boron concentration. For other power regimes, a simple “curtain management” for control rods have been implemented, which means that all the control rods are inserted at the same level. No axial power profile management has been studied in PRATIC-b yet. Contrary to the SBF PRATIC [3], not all the assemblies incorporate absorber rod clusters as shown in figure 3 (44 %, with 52 % shutdown rods). However, all the rods use AIC materials which maximise the absorbing efficiency compared to steel control rod materials.

Figure 2 : Fuel zoning map (a), reloading pattern (b) and location of absorbing rod banks (c).

4. RESULTS FOR THE EQUILIBRIUM CYCLE

4.1. Equilibrium cycle length and burnup distribution

CRONOS2 predicts an equilibrium cycle length of 17.08 GWd/t (i.e 708.3 Equivalent Full Power Day EFPD) which is 1.2 % and 1.8 % less than with APOLLO3 and SIMULATE. Theses cycle durations are

within the range of the cycle length of the SBF PRATIC core which was established using CRONOS2 at 17.15 GWd/t in 2024 [3] and with the SIMULATE5 at 17.45 GWd/t employing JEFF-3.1.1 library [4]. The average assembly wise and axially integrated burnup values are represented at the beginning of cycle (BOC) with CRONOS2 code in figure 4. The average burnup of the discharged assemblies among the three codes are between 14.87 GWd/t and 16.76 GWd/t at BOC and 31.68 GWd/t and 34.26 GWd/t at EOC. Axially integrated burnup has a maximum of 34.47 GWd/t to 37.88 GWd/t which translates to a maximum close to 43 GWd/t at pin level depending of the code.

Figure 3 : Fuel assembly scale distribution of the radial burnup in PRATIC at BOC with CRONOS2.

4.2. Reactivity control and boron concentration

The critical boron concentration evolution is displayed in figure 5 and its value at the BOC is equal to 1461 ppm for CRONOS2, 1455 ppm for APOLLO3 and 1476 ppm for SIMULATE5. One can draw from this figure the differential boron concentration evolution, which varies between -83.6 ppm/GWd/t (-2.05 ppm/EFPD) for APOLLO3 and -84.9 ppm/GWd/t (-2.08 ppm/EFPD) for CRONOS2. A higher differential boron concentration for CRONOS2 reflects the lower cycle length for this last calculation. A -6.77 pcm/ppm and -8.29 pcm/ppm boron efficiency was obtained with CRONOS2 at BOC and at EOC respectively, which means an 83 pcm reactivity reserve at EOC close to the SBF PRATIC EOC criteria of 100 pcm. A higher boron differential efficiency at the end of the cycle is typical for PWR technology [18]. The introduction of soluble boron in the core can deteriorate the moderator temperature reactivity effect, especially when boron is most present in the BOC. CRONOS2 estimates a moderator temperature reactivity effect of -22.4 pcm/°C at BOC and -59.4 pcm/°C at EOC, which is coherent with moderator temperature coefficient MTC values found in large PWR [18] and well below the criteria of a positive feedback. At the exception of the BOC where a faster reactivity loss is observed, the reactivity and boron concentration loss rhythms are linear throughout the cycle. The faster drop of reactivity at BOC could be explained by the gadolinium peak of the external assembly and by the apparition of fission product (except ^{135}I - ^{135}Xe that were saturated). The position of the gadolinium peak depends on the enrichment in ^{235}U of the fuel: an enrichment of 5.0 wt% would conduct to a gadolinium peak around 17.5 GWd/t, whereas a 2.5 wt% in ^{235}U would imply a gadolinium peak close to 10 GWd/t [4]. Thus, two gadolinium peaks could be expected, one from the central and internal assembly during their first cycle and one from external assembly at the end of their first cycle and when refuelled, where their average discharged burnup should be close to 17.5 GWd/t. The presence of only eight gadolinium poisoned fuel pins lead to no significant change to the reactivity loss rhythm, compared to SBF PRATIC where an average of thirty gadolinium pins were loaded [3].

In terms of reactivity control, slightly smaller gaps are observed with PRATIC-b than with SBF PRATIC among the three codes. Indeed, a maximum difference of 37 ppm was exhibited between CRONOS2 and SIMULATE5 resulting in approximately +262 pcm of reactivity surplus, which is within the -182 pcm/+298 pcm reactivity interval found with SBF PRATIC [4].

Figure 4 : Evolution of the critical boron concentration in the equilibrium cycle (top) and differences to CRONOS2 calculation (bottom).

4.3. Core power distribution

The local power peak factors are used as intermediate observables in order to deduce margins for normal and incidental operation of the core. Power factors are computed from the normalization of the power distribution and can be calculated at pin or assembly level in two or three dimensions.

- $^{MAX,PIN}F_{XY}$: The 2D pin scale power peak enables the computation of the margin to the departure from nucleate boiling by calculating the ratio of critical heat flux and the local heat flux using thermohydraulic correlation.
- $^{MAX,PIN}F_Q$: From the 3D pin scale power peak factor, one can deduce the margin to cladding rupture or local melting of fuel using the equivalent linear power peak factor:

$$^{MAX,PIN}P_{LIN} = ^{MAX,PIN}F_Q \times ^{AVE}P_{lin}$$

As the thermohydraulic conditions are the same as in the SBF PRATIC [3] core, an equivalent power peak factor performance was initially aimed. The $^{MAX,PIN}F_{XY}$ and the $^{MAX,PIN}F_Q$ are drawn in the figures 6 along with the axial offset. The maximum $^{MAX,PIN}F_{XY}$ is established at BOC at 1.50 using CRONOS2 and at 1.52 with APOLLO3 and SIMULATE5, well below the saturation power factor equal to 2.038 [3], showing a margin of 25.57 % similar to SBF PRATIC (24.29 %) [3]. The $^{MAX,PIN}F_Q$ reaches a maximum within the range of 1.96-1.98 also at BOC, leading to a maximum of linear power between 226.7 and 229.9 W/cm, showing closer results among codes than with SBF PRATIC [4]. These values are far below the threshold that could conduct to a cladding rupture (420-430 W/cm) or to the fuel melting (590 W/cm) [19]. Greater margins are demonstrated in PRATIC-b compared to SBF PRATIC [3] due to a less skewed axial power. The same decreasing monotonic function of time can be observed for the $^{MAX,PIN}F_{XY}$ and the $^{MAX,PIN}F_Q$, which was not the case in SBF PRATIC [3], where the $^{MAX,PIN}F_Q$ showed three peaks: at BOC, during the gadolinium peak and at EOC when the power surge at the top of the core. Here the gadolinium peak doesn't provoke any increase of local power peak factor, which is coherent with the absence of reactivity surge seen before. Moreover, the drift of axial offset (figure 6) is limited with all the codes to less than one percent in contrast to the 60 % drift in SBF PRATIC compute with CRONOS2 [3]. The maximum $^{MAX,PIN}F_{XY}$ and $^{MAX,PIN}F_Q$ at BOC and EOC are observed in the first cycle external assembly (D09 and H09 at BOC), at the middle of the fissile height at BOC then 40 cm higher at EOC, and at the edge of the assembly directed toward the centre of the core.

Smaller discrepancies are observed on the power peak factor with PRATIC-b compared to SBF PRATIC, particularly on the $^{MAX,PIN}F_Q$. Indeed, for this observable, the maximum absolute relative difference is only of 2.6 % with PRATIC-b against 9.4 % with SBF PRATIC [4]. This can be explained, by the lack of

rod insertion to control reactivity and by the fewer burnable absorbers, on which bias has been exhibited in SBF PRATIC [4], that significantly changes the power distribution in the core.

Figure 5 : Evolution of the $^{MAX, PIN}F_{XY}$ (a), the $^{MAX, PIN}F_0$ (b) and the axial offset (c) during the equilibrium cycle (top) and differences to the CRONOS2 calculation (bot). The normalised axially integrate power distribution is shown in (d) with the code CRONOS2 at BOC.

5. CONCLUSIONS

A new core design was developed for the PRATIC benchmark in this paper in order to propose a simpler SMR industrial-grade neutronic design to host code-to-code comparison than a SBF reactor type. The new core, called PRATIC-b, was presented and its equilibrium cycle was computed using three deterministic code systems: APOLLO2-CRONOS2, APOLLO3 and CMS5. PRATIC-b equilibrium cycle was characterised and the three codes showed good agreement on the analysed observables. Specially, differences of power peak estimations between codes were closer using soluble boron reactivity control rather than control rods as in SBF PRATIC.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The author would like to thank CEA's COSMR project for hosting this activity. Moreover, they would like to expand they thanks to the SIGAR development team for they availability and their dedication. Many thanks to the development teams of the "BEAVRS" and "VERA Core Physics" benchmarks, whose work has been used as a base for some input data.

REFERENCES

- [1] "Sabey considers Sodium deployment at its data centres" (2025) <https://www.world-nuclear-news.org/articles/sabey-considers-sodium-deployment-at-its-data-centres>.
- [2] C.A. Lloyd, T. Roulstone, R.E. Lyons, "Transport, constructability, and economic advantages of SMR modularization", *Prog. Nucl. Energy* **134**, 103672 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pnucene.2021.103672>
- [3] R. Vuiart, A. Eustache, S. Eveillard, G. Prulhière, "PRATIC: A soluble-boron-free, pressurized water cooled, SMR core benchmark", *EPJ Nuclear Sci. Technol.* **10**, 25 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1051/epjn/2024026>
- [4] R. Vuiart, Q. Besson, F. Bernard, S. Bonthoux, G. Prulhière, "Modeling the Equilibrium Cycle of the PRATIC SMR Core Benchmark Using the CMS5 Code System", In *Proceedings of ICAPP 2025*, Antibes – Juan les Pins, France.
- [5] "EASI-SMR", URL <https://easi-smr.eu/>.
- [6] "Working Party on Scientific Issues and Uncertainty Analysis of Reactor Systems (WPRS)", URL https://www.oecd-nea.org/jcms/c_12832/working-party-on-scientific-issues-and-uncertainty-analysis-of-reactor-systems-wprs.
- [7] R. Sanchez, J. Mondot, Z. Stancovski, A. Cos-Sic, I. Zmijarevic, "APOLLO2: A user-oriented, portable, modular code for multi-group transport assembly calculations", *Nucl. Sci. Eng.* **100**, 352 (1988).
- [8] J. J. Lautard et al., "CRONOS: A modular computational system for neutronic core calculations", *IAEA Top. Mtg.*, 1990, Cadarache, France, 1990.
- [9] P. Mosca et al. "APOLLO3®: Overview of the New Code Capabilities for Reactor Physics Analysis." *Nuclear Science and Engineering*, pp. 1–14 (2024).
- [10] J. Rhodes, K. Smith, and D. Lee, "CASMO-5 Development and Applications," In *Proceeding Int. Conf. on Advances in Nuclear Analysis and Simulation (PHYSOR 2006)*, Vancouver, BC, Canada, Sept. 10-14 (2006)
- [11] T. Bahadir and S.-Ö. Lindhal, "Studsvik's Next Generation Nodal Code SIMULATE-5," In *Proc. Advances in Nuclear Fuel Management IV (ANFM IV)*, Hilton Head, SC, USA, April 12-15 (2009).
- [12] A. Santamarina, D. Bernard, P. Blaise, P. Leconte, R. Le Tellier, C. Vaglio-Gaudard, J.-F. Vidal, "APOLLO2.8: A validated code package for PWR neutronics calculations (2009)", In *Proceedings Int. Conf. ANFM*, 2009 Vol. 2, p. 04.
- [13] A. Santamarina et al, "The JEFF3.1.1 Nuclear Data Library. Validation Results from JEF2.2 to JEFF-3.1.1", *OECD 2009 NEA No. 6807*, ISBN 978- 92-64-99074-6, 01 2009.
- [14] A.M. Baudron, J.J. Lautard, "MINOS: a simplified Pn Solver for Core Calculation", *Nucl. Sci. Eng.* **155**, 250 (2007).
- [15] N. Gérard Castaing, E. Ménédeu, B. Mathon, A. Rouchon, N. Zaim, C. Vaglio-Gaudard, "SIGAR: An APOLLO3® -Based Framework for PWR Analysis", In *Proceeding Int. Conf. M&C*, 2025.
- [16] CEA, *Neutronics. e-den*, A Nuclear Energy Division Monograph, Editions Le Moniteur, 2015. ISBN 978-2-281-11372-3. URL "https://www.cea.fr/english/Documents/scientific-and-economic-publications/nuclear-energy-monographs/CEA_Monograph4_Neutronics_2015_GB.pdf".
- [17] M. Asgari, T. Bahadir, D. Kropaczek, E. Gibson, J. Williams, "Analysis of the Pin Power Peaking of the Hatch Unit 1 Cycle 21 Failed Fuel Assemblies." In *Proceedings of 2010 LWR Fuel Performance/TopFuel/WRFP*, September 26-29, 2010, Orlando, Florida, USA, (2010).
- [18] H. Grard, *Physique, fonctionnement et sûreté des REP - le réacteur en production*. EDP Sciences, 2014. URL "<https://laboutique.edpsciences.fr/produit/738/9782759817009/physique-fonctionnement-et-surete-des-rep>"
- [19] CEA, *Nuclear Fuels. e-den*, A Nuclear Energy Division Monograph. Editions Le Moniteur, 2009. ISBN 978-2-281-11345-7. URL "https://www.cea.fr/english/Documents/scientific-and-economic-publications/nuclear-energy-monographs/CEA_Monograph2_Nuclear-fuels_2009_GB.pdf".